

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

doi: [10.15497/RDA000101](https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA000101)

RDA for Research Data Management (RDM) Support and Education

Celebrating A Decade of Data
RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop

Version: November 2023

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for Research Data Management (RDM) Support and Education', brought chairs and members of RDA community groups together, with members of the wider research data community, to share and discuss challenges, solutions, and initiatives associated with providing data management support and education for researchers and data professionals. The key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

CHALLENGES TO BE ADDRESSED WITHIN THE THEME OF RDM SUPPORT AND EDUCATION

Engagement

- Understanding RDM needs of researchers.
- Providing disciplinary and sub-disciplinary support that adequately covers diversity of data.
- Researchers from some disciplines e.g., Arts, Humanities, Social Sciences (HASS) and Cultural Heritage, do not typically see their research outputs as 'data'.
- Lack of funding and human resources to encourage busy/ overwhelmed researchers to invest time and effort in RDM practices, such as creating [Data Management Plans \(DMPs\)](#).
- Ensuring that all researchers, regardless of career stage, are educated about the value and importance of good RDM practice.
- Acquiring feedback from researchers to learn what engagement activities were beneficial.

Training and education

- RDM training is not typically embedded within institutional curricula.
- Inconsistent RDM training approaches adopted at institutional, national and international level.
- Low researcher participation in non-compulsory RDM workshops and e-learning modules.
- Lack of incentive (reward and recognition) for researchers to participate in RDM training.
- Many good training resources and initiatives exist but need updating, maintaining, and documenting to retain long-term value.
- Connecting researchers to resources so data support professionals can provide help easily and efficiently.
- Providing targeted needs-related training and professional support in a timely manner.

Professional support

- RDM support professionals siloed and unconnected with other institutional services.
- Lack of clarity about policies, roles, and responsibilities of data support professionals.
- Data support roles often overlap or not formally unrecognised leading to 'hidden' work.
- Need to define interoperable roles and responsibilities of data stewards at global level.
- Providing disciplinary data stewardship and meeting specific needs of researchers. Many data stewards provide generic RDM support.
- Professionalisation of data stewardship and establishment of career tracks.
- Lack of information about data stewardship models and how to implement them effectively.

PARTICIPATING GROUP & WORKSHOP LEAD*

[CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries \(SoRDS\) IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Hugh Shanahan](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Early Career and Engagement IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Devan Donaldson](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Magdalena Szuflińska](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Engaging Researchers with Data IG](#)

Workshop lead(s): [Shannon Sheridan](#) & [James Savage](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Libraries for Research Data IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Su Nee Goh](#)

[See community group card](#)

[Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)

Workshop lead: [Liise Lehtsalu](#)

[See community group card](#)

*The workshop lead(s) collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop and explained them during the workshop on behalf of their group.

SOLUTIONS TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES

RDA groups

- Continue to map and cluster RDA groups to identify similarities and differences, and enable the exchange of knowledge, best practices and cross-fertilisation of ideas.
- Prioritise collaboration between RDA groups working on RDM support and education related topics.
- RDA groups to submit joint Plenary meeting session applications where beneficial.
- Liaise with the Reproducibility Interest Group on the relationship between reproducible research and RDM.

Training activities

- Provide RDM support and education from the researcher's perspective to ensure researcher's training needs are met.
- Provide practical 'needs-related' RDM training for researchers so they can implement skills and lessons learned in their specific research context.
- Make RDM training, e.g., data literacy skills, for researchers and data support professionals mandatory within institutions, taking a top-down and bottom-up approach, if possible.
- Incorporate Open Science concepts and [FAIR data principles](#) in RDM support and education efforts to highlight benefits of RDM on research integrity and reproducible research.

Training resources

- Utilise educational material at [FAIRsharing](#) to help guide various research roles to discovery of standards, databases and data policies.
- Develop more resources like the [FAIR cookbook for Life Sciences](#) to efficiently collect and share expertise.
- Document training resources with rich metadata to ensure that they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).
- Build capacity for accessing funding to support the production and maintenance of RDM training resources.
- Facilitate the production of training material as part of research projects to be used in specific contexts.

Research Evaluation

- Incentivise researchers to participate in training by providing institutional credits.
- Consider participation in RDM training activities in academic evaluation process within institutions.
- Continue to work towards the recognition of 'FAIR' (Reusable) research outputs.

Professional support

- Ensure that data support professionals, e.g., data stewards, are recognised as integral research project members and involved in the project management process from start to end.
- Monitor and recognise the various data support roles and responsibilities within different institutions in order to track efforts by those not formally recognised as a 'data steward'.
- Consider the lessons learned from provision of professional support for research software engineering.

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Increase the number of Domain Ambassadors.

Establish the [Domain Ambassador Interest Group \(IG\)](#) as a consequence of the [Birds of a Feather session](#) at the RDA's 21st Plenary meeting.

Coordinate an RDM Support and Education Speaker Series.

Invite international speakers to a webinar series share their success stories and lessons learned of implementing institutional RDM frameworks and/or data stewardship models with the RDA community.

Establish training resource validation consultation groups.

Establish international disciplinary consultation groups to identify, evaluate, and validate locally created training resources and ensure they meets disciplinary needs on a broad scale.

Collect data stewardship case studies.

- Publish case studies describing the roles and responsibilities of data stewards.
- Create a crosswalk of different models of data stewardship within research institutions.
- Provide a 'toolkit'; guidance and best practices for how to implement data stewardship within an research institution.

Collect regional RDM support and education case studies.

Collect case studies showcasing how RDM support and education is organised by different countries and regions.

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

- [An international consensus on effective, inclusive, and career-spanning short-format training in the life sciences and beyond](#) - Publication
- [CESSDA](#)
- [Digital Research Skills Australasia \(DRSA\)](#)
- [ELIXIR](#)
- [Engaging Researchers with Data Management: The Cookbook](#)
- [EOSC Task Forces](#)
- [FAIRassist.org](#) - educational component of [FAIRSharing](#)
- [FAIR-IMPACT](#)
- [FAIR cookbook for Life Sciences](#)
- [FAIR teaching handbook](#) - FAIRsFAIR
- [French Recherche Data Gouv initiative](#)
- [Horizon Europe](#)
- [How to engage researchers in data management plans](#) - RDA France workshop 2022
- [IDEA: Improving Data Engagement and Advocacy](#) - Podcast
- [Institute of Museum and Library Services \(IMLS\)](#) - Funding agency

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INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST CONT.

- [Institutional Underpinnings Research Data Management Network](#) (ARDC)
- [National Science Foundation \(NSF\)](#)
- [Open Educational Resources \(OER\)](#) commons & similar initiatives
- [Re3data.org](#)
- [Research Data Management Services Unit](#) MDC, Berlin
- [Research Infrastructure Self Evaluation \(RISE\) Framework](#) by DCC
- [RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship - Current Models of Data Stewardship: Survey Report](#)
- [RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship - Data Stewardship Landscape Report](#)
- [Resource Matrix](#)
- [Skills4EOSC](#)
- [Terms4FAIRskills](#)
- [The State of Open Data 2023](#) Report
- [Training eSupport System \(TeSS\)](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things for various disciplines](#)

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For more information about the RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop series, please contact Community Development Manager, Connie Clare (connie.clare@rda-foundation.org)

To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#)